

Development and Control of a Flying Ejector-pin System with Local Gain-Scheduling ILC Scheme

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Abstract—The MiniLED mass transfer process requires high-speed and high-precision devices to guarantee mass production and precise mounting. The motivation of this paper is to combine the ability to enable the mechanical transfer approaches to run in the manner of continuous manipulation to increase efficiency. The developed system achieves this objective by proposing a compliant flying ejector-pin transfer (CFET) strategy, whose performance is enhanced by a novel local gain-scheduling iterative learning control (LGS-ILC) scheme. First, a CFET strategy is proposed, which is achieved by incorporating synchronous motion into the flip-chip-on-board (flip-COB) transfer method. Then, the development of a flying ejector-pin system is presented, including system design and its working principle. Next, to provide high-speed and high-accuracy tracking controls for CFET implementation, a first-step vibration (FSV) behavior is analytically identified and modeled to capture the dynamic characteristics of the system in the case of high-speed trajectory tracking by ILC-based motion control. Thereafter, to address this behavior, a novel LGS-ILC is designed, which improves the tracking performance by predicting and suppressing FSV. Besides, the convergence of LGS-ILC and control system are analyzed in theory. Finally, a series of verification tests were carried out, including experimental validation of LGS-ILC and closed-loop CFET experiments. The results indicate that the LGS-ILC can effectively improve the performance in high-speed trajectory tracking. Besides, the transfer period and accuracy of the developed system are achieved as 50 ms and $\pm 2.5 \mu\text{m}$ respectively, uniformly proving that high-efficiency continuous manipulation is achieved.

Index Terms—Flexure-based compliant mechanism, motion control, iterative learning control, MiniLED, mass transfer

I. INTRODUCTION

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Fig. 1. Schematics of MiniLED mass transfer. (a) The process of MiniLED mass transfer. (b) Flip-COB transfer system. (c) The process of flip-COB transfer.

WITH the arrival of “ultra-HD display era”, the MiniLED chips have emerged and been widely used on display panels, due to the outstanding performances of high range ratio (HDR), thin profile, and low consumption [1]. However, the production efficiency of MiniLED display is greatly restricted by the mass transfer process, which requires transferring tens of millions of chips from wafer to substrate with a high yield rate ($< 99.99\%$) within a short duration [2]. Due to the tiny size ($100 \mu\text{m}$) of the chips and compact array ($150 \mu\text{m}$) as shown in Fig.1(a), it is hard to achieve a mechanical transfer system that provides high-dynamics motion in terms of high-accuracy (transfer error $< \pm 5 \mu\text{m}$) and high-speed to implement mass transfer [3]. Therefore, developing a system that meets these performance requirements is crucial for achieving high-throughput MiniLED mass transfer.

To catch for this requirement, various pioneering studies have been carried out to increase the transfer efficiency by the mechanical approaches. Generally, they can be grouped into two categories. One approach is the pick & place transfer strategy, which first picks up the LED chips by a conveyor arm from the wafer, and then places them onto the substrate [4], [5]. In high-speed reciprocal transfer motions, the degree of harmonic oscillation in the conveyor arm is positively correlated with its operational speed. Another method is the flip-COB transfer strategy, where the wafer is flipped and then transferred by using a needle [6], [7], as shown in Fig.1(b) and Fig.1(c). This method involves intermittent high-frequency

start-stop motions, which will cause harmonic oscillation in the transfer system and lead to position drift of the chip array.

In a word, subject to the inherent dynamics, current mechanical transfer methods are restricted to a start-stop manipulation rather than continuous operation, aimed at attenuating these dynamics [8], [9]. Fortunately, this problem could be solved by utilizing the flexure-based compliant mechanism, thanks to its excellent advantages of compact size, no assembly, and no friction [10], [11]. To this end, in this work, a flying ejector-pin system is developed for high-speed and high-precision continuous transfer, i.e., the CFET strategy.

From the viewpoint of control design, the tracking accuracy of flexure-based nanopositioning systems is greatly limited by the inherent nonlinear hysteresis behavior, especially during high-speed trajectory tracking, for instance, the flexible transfer manipulator in this work. To address hysteresis compensation, considerable research has focused on inversion-based feedforward control methods, which require sufficient prior knowledge of the hysteresis dynamics [12], [13]. However, these approaches suffer from modeling complexity and parameter sensitivity [14]. Considering the repetitive motion of the compliant mechanism, ILC could be employed for hysteresis compensation, as it learns the system dynamics without needing explicit modeling [15], [16]. In high-speed nanopositioning applications, ILC provides robust support for hysteresis rejection [17], [18]. Nevertheless, most existing research has utilized nanopositioners with high mechanical bandwidth, significantly exceeding the learnable bandwidth. There is limited research on scenarios where the learnable bandwidth is close to the first resonant mode, a challenge arising from high-speed trajectory tracking and large strokes of compliant mechanisms [19]. To address this problem, a FSV behavior is first established, followed by proposing a novel LGS-ILC to suppress the FSV to reduce the error in high-speed trajectory tracking. The proposed LGS-ILC is achieved by identifying the damping ratio of plant to enhance the performance, akin to the modified ILC methods that incorporate prior knowledge, such as model prediction [20] and energy-selected [21].

The main contribution of this work is the development of a flying ejector-pin system for continuous transfer, with performance improvements achieved by a novel LGS-ILC. The rest of the paper is organized as follows: in section II, the CFET strategy is presented; the design and working principle of the flying ejector-pin system are demonstrated in section III; section IV devotes to controller design; in section V, a series of validation experiments and performance evaluations are illustrated. Finally, section VI concludes this work.

II. COMPLIANT FLYING EJECTOR-PIN TRANSFER STRATEGY

Here, a CFET strategy is developed by enabling continuous manipulation of the flip-COB transfer method. As shown in Fig.2(a), the flip-COB transfer process can be viewed as a start-stop manipulation, consisting of two point-to-point motions (duration $[t_0, t_1]$ and $[t_2, t_3]$) and one standstill motion (duration $[t_1, t_2]$). Assuming the trajectory of substrate

Fig. 2. Schematic illustration of transfer strategy. (a) Flip-COB transfer strategy. (b) CFET strategy.

conveying motion stage is shaped via symmetric velocity planning, the stage velocity $v_m(t)$ can be expressed as:

$$v_m(t) = \begin{cases} v_d - v_a(t), & t_0 \leq t < t_1 \\ 0, & t_1 \leq t < t_2 \\ v_a(t), & t_2 \leq t < t_3 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $v_a(t)$ is variable velocity over time and v_d is a constant velocity. According to (1), to minimize the impact of harmonic oscillation caused by velocity variations, it is essential to optimize $v_a(t)$. However, the constraints of high-speed motion and the short duration of start-stop manipulation restrict the applicability of high-order shaping approaches for $v_a(t)$, leading to limited optimization results. In a word, the point-to-point motion greatly limited the efficiency of the flip-COB transfer strategy.

To address this issue, a novel CFET strategy is proposed, as shown in Fig.2(b). The key improvement is enabling the substrate conveying motion stage to maintain a constant velocity ($v_m(t) = v_d$) throughout the process, thereby avoiding point-to-point motion. To achieve this, the needle is required to follow a 2-DOF trajectory controlled by the manipulator. After initial alignment at $t = t_0$, the needle performs continuous transfer: the horizontal direction moves synchronously during $[t_1, t_2]$, while the vertical direction executes reciprocating motion similar to the flip-COB transfer strategy. Upon completing the chip transfer, the needle returns to its original position and aligns with the next chip. This approach transitions the transfer system from start-stop manipulation to continuous movement, thereby reducing harmonic oscillations and allowing for a higher transfer efficiency.

III. DEVELOPMENT OF FLYING EJECTOR-PIN SYSTEM

A. System design

1) *Flying ejector-pin system*: The flying ejector-pin system is designed as shown in Fig.3(a), which consists of a flexible transfer manipulator, motion stage, wafer jig, and vision system. The motion stage, which provides 4-DOF movement ($XYZ\theta$), aligns and conveys the wafer tape to the needle. The vision system, equipped with an industrial camera and a focuser, establishes the global coordinates of the wafer tape and observes the transfer results. The flexible transfer manipulator ensures the synchronous motion of the needle,

Fig. 3. Schematics of the designed flying ejector-pin system. (a) Assembly diagram. (b) Flexible transfer manipulator. (c) Wafer jig.

Fig. 4. Design of flexible transfer manipulator. (a) The bridge-type based serial compliant mechanism. (b) Half of single-axis module. (c) Flexure components.

as shown in Fig.3(b). A vacuum adsorption unit (VAU) is mounted on the manipulator to handle the high-frequency interaction forces between the wafer tape and the needle. The wafer jig, shown in Fig.3(c), secures the wafer tape and levels it using four adjustment bolts.

2) *Flexible transfer manipulator*: The flexible transfer manipulator is achieved by designing a bridge-type based serial compliant mechanism, as shown in Fig.4(a). The displacement of manipulator is generated by a pair of piezo-actuators (PZTs). For the structure of the compliant mechanism, a symmetric X-axis module is serially combined with a Z-axis module of the same design, as shown in Fig.4(b). A compact linear guideway to minimize parasitic motion is mounted on the Z-axis module, as shown in Fig.3(b). The manipulator is constructed from aluminum alloy Al-7075T6, chosen for its high ratio of fatigue stress to Young's modulus ($\sigma_{Fa}/E = 0.31\%$) and low density ($\sigma = 2810 \text{ kg/m}^3$). The flexure components include flexure hinges and flexure beams, as shown in Fig.4(c). For the dimension parameters of the compliant mechanism, its optimization aims to maximize the travel range and natural frequency. The final design specifications are as follows. X-axis: stroke $275.2 \mu\text{m}$ and natural frequency 176 Hz ; Z-axis: stroke $423.6 \mu\text{m}$ and natural frequency 294 Hz .

3) *Vacuum adsorption unit*: The assembly diagram of VAU is displayed in Fig.5(a). The needle is fixed on the end-effector of the compliant mechanism by a bushing, while the body is mounted to the rigid beam of Z-axis. The vacuum is generated through the insert fitting to handle the plastic deformation of

Fig. 5. Schematics of the VAU. (a) The assembly diagram. (b) Plastic deformation of wafer tape.

Fig. 6. Workflow of the proposed CFET strategy. (a) \rightarrow (b) chip transfer, (b) \rightarrow (c) transfer return, (c) \rightarrow (d) alignment of the next chip.

the tape caused by the interaction force between wafer tape and needle. This deformation will result in position deviation of the chip array, as shown in Fig.5(b).

B. Working Principle Demonstration

Based on the proposed CFET strategy, the working principle of the system is illustrated in Fig.6. The horizontal and vertical directions are defined as the X-axis and Z-axis, respectively. Let U_x and U_z denote the control signals for the PZTs, with associated output forces f_x and f_z , the working principle of CFET is described as follows:

(a) \rightarrow (b) The Z-axis moves forward to transfer the chip from the wafer tape to the substrate, while the X-axis moves at a constant velocity, covering half of the chip pitch Δd . During this process, the VAU is turned "on" to protect the chip array;

(b) \rightarrow (c) The Z-axis moves backward to return the needle to its original position, while the X-axis continues its motion as before. Once the needle has completely disengaged from the wafer tape, the VAU is turned "off";

(c) \rightarrow (d) The Z-axis remains in the original position, and the X-axis moves backward to align the next chip. The X-axis

Fig. 7. Control system diagram of flying ejector-pin system.

Fig. 8. Control issue. (a) Vibration under ILC-based trajectory tracking. (b) FSV behavior. (c) Limited learnable band of lightly damping resonating system.

displacement in this step is Δd . The transfer process then repeats by cycling through steps (a) \rightarrow (d).

IV. CONTROLLER DESIGN

The main purpose of this section is to present the controller design of the system. The control system is demonstrated first, followed by introduction of the proposed LGS-ILC.

The control system is designed as shown in Fig. 7. The trajectory for the flexible transfer manipulator is generated using the seventh-degree polynomial shaping method and then converted into the motion stage commands. The VAU employs event-triggered control, activating based on the trajectory period. In terms of the flexible transfer manipulator, due to the serial kinematics of the compliant mechanism, the controller design is simplified to a single-DOF controller. This controller integrates the LGS-ILC with a proportional-integral (PI) feedback controller. The nonlinear hysteresis is addressed by the repetitive LGS-ILC, while robustness is improved by the PI controller, and system damping is achieved through positive positioning feedback (PPF) control.

A. Control issue of first step vibration behavior

Here, the FSV behavior of ILC is first presented, followed by the problem of FSV rejection via the feedback controller.

1) *FSV behavior of ILC*: Generally, the ILC regulates control output iteratively to obtain perfect tracking. A common approach is Proportional-ILC (P-ILC), which employs an update law in the frequency domain:

$$U_{j+1}(s) = Q(s)[U_j(s) + \gamma E_j(s)] \quad (2)$$

where $U_j(s)$ and $E_j(s)$ are the control output and tracking error in the j^{th} trial, respectively. $Q(s)$ is the robust filter, and γ is the learning gain. According to [22], the stability of ILC is characterized by the monotonic decay of the tracking error, which is guaranteed by satisfying the following convergence condition:

$$|Q(s)[1 - \gamma G(s)]| < 1 \quad (3)$$

where $|Q(s)[1 - \gamma G(s)]|$ is the amplitude of tracking error between two successive iterations. Normally, the zero-phase low-pass filter is adopted for $Q(s)$ to cut-off the frequencies that do not satisfy (3).

Without loss of generality, assuming that the desired output $y_d(t)$ is predetermined over the duration $t \in [0, T]$. In high-speed trajectory tracking with nanopositioning systems, sharp variations in the reference signal often lead to vibrations in the initial stages of the learning process. These vibrations typically worsen with an increasing number of iterations, as shown in Fig. 8(a). This phenomenon is caused by the mutational signal of control output during $[u_j(T), u_{j+1}(0)]$, which result from the update law of ILC, as illustrated in Fig. 8(b). Based on the dynamics characteristics, this phenomenon is termed FSV in this paper. Considering the robust filter $Q(s)$, (2) is rewritten as:

$$\tau \mathbf{u}_{j+1} = \mathbf{Q} \otimes (\tau \mathbf{u}_j + \tau \mathbf{L}_j) \quad (4)$$

where $\tau \mathbf{u}_i = [\mathbf{u}_1 \ \mathbf{u}_2 \ \dots \ \mathbf{u}_{i-1} \ \mathbf{u}_i]^T$, $\mathbf{u}_i = \{t \in [0, T] | u_j(t)\}$, $\tau \mathbf{L}_i = [\mathbf{L}_1 \ \mathbf{L}_2 \ \dots \ \mathbf{L}_{i-1} \ \mathbf{L}_i]^T$, $\mathbf{L}_i = \{t \in [0, T] | \gamma e_j(t)\}$, and $\mathbf{Q} = \text{diag}[Q(t), Q(t), \dots, Q(t)]_{(j+1) \times (j+1)}$. From (4), it is obtained that the signals in different iterations (between j^{th} and $j+1^{\text{th}}$) cannot be filtered by $Q(s)$, i.e. over the duration $[u_j(T), u_{j+1}(0)]$. Moreover, due to lightly damping resonating dynamics, the learnable band (ω_c) must be lower than the first resonant frequency of plant (ω_n), meaning that residual vibration caused by the FSV cannot enter into the learning filter, as shown in Fig. 8(c). Thus, based on this analysis, FSV is an unavoidable phenomenon when using ILC to regulate the plant.

Even worse, the impact of FSV is deteriorated by the large flexure of the compliant mechanism. To ensure sufficient stroke for flexible transfer manipulator, a large flexure is required, and the displacement is designed as follows:

$$d_m = \frac{k_a}{k_a + k_m} d_a \quad (5)$$

where d_m and d_a are the maximum displacement of compliant mechanism and PZT respectively, and k_m and k_a are their corresponding stiffness. According to (5), to achieve a flexible transfer manipulator with a large stroke, k_m should be decreased, resulting in:

Fig. 9. Control system diagram of current-type ILC.

$$\omega_n = \sqrt{k_m/m} = 1/\sqrt{c_m m} \quad (6)$$

where m is the mass, and $c_m = 1/k_m$ is the compliance. According to (6), a larger flexure results in a lower natural frequency. Therefore, the FSV attenuation will persist over an extended period, with the attenuation factor being $1/\omega_n$.

To reduce the effect of FSV, the learning gain has to be limited, which restricts convergence performance. For a lightly damping resonating system $G(s)$ with open-loop gain K_o and assuming $Q(s) = 1$ within the learnable band, in the low-frequency range where $s \rightarrow 0$, it can be derived from (3) as:

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow 0} |Q(s) [1 - \gamma G(s)]| = |1 - \gamma K_o| \quad (7)$$

From (7), to achieve better convergence of ILC, the γ should be set as close to $1/K_o$ as possible. Besides, to avoid control saturation, the learning gain should satisfy $\gamma \leq 1/K_o$. Therefore, reducing γ to mitigate the effect of FSV will lead to degraded convergence performance. In a word, it is crucial to both suppress FSV and ensure a large γ to achieve high tracking accuracy in ILC, in the presence of a limited learnable band and high-speed tracking requirements.

2) *FSV rejection by feedback control*: To address FSV, another method is to integrate feedback control into ILC, known as current-type ILC. In this case, FSV acts as an input disturbance characterized by a square wave with a variable magnitude d , as shown in Fig.9. Define the transfer function of feedback controller and plant as:

$$C(s) = A(s)/B(s), G(s) = N(s)/D(s) \quad (8)$$

Since closed-loop stability is independent of ILC, the effort of the feedback controller to FSV can be evaluated by the input disturbance sensitivity:

$$\begin{aligned} S_i(s) &= \frac{y(s)}{d(s)} = \frac{G(s)}{1 + C(s)G(s)} \\ &= \frac{N(s)}{D(s)} \frac{D(s)B(s)}{D(s)B(s) + N(s)A(s)} \\ &= \frac{N(s)B(s)}{D(s)B(s) + N(s)A(s)} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

By (9), the lightly damping resonant poles $D(s)$ are analytically canceled by the closed-loop. This indicates that the resonating mode in $D(s)$ will be excited by FSV, necessitating a sufficient margin for system stabilization to handle the unknown amplitude FSV. This limitation is further deteriorated under low control bandwidth. Finally, the aforementioned

Fig. 10. Control system diagram of LGS-ILC.

constraint leads to low feedback control effort, indicating that FSV cannot be effectively addressed through feedback control alone.

B. Local Gain-Scheduling Iterative Learning Control

In this section, the FSV behavior is first modeled, followed by the design of LGS-ILC to address this issue. Besides, the convergence of LGS-ILC and the control system is proven theoretically.

1) *Design of LGS-ILC*: Based on the mutational characteristic illustrated in Fig.8(b), the FSV behavior can be equivalent to the step response of a lightly damping resonating system. According to control theory, the maximum amplitude of the response, occurring at the moment of overshoot, can be expressed as:

$$A_{os} = A_o K_o (1 + \sigma) = A_o K_o \left(1 + e^{\frac{-\xi\pi}{\sqrt{1-\xi^2}}} \right) \quad (10)$$

where ξ is the damping ratio of the plant, A_o is the amplitude of control input, and K_o is the open-loop gain of the plant. It is obvious that the degree of overshoot is related to the inherent property ξ . By (2) and (10), assuming $|Q(s)| = 1$ within the learnable band, the maximum value of FSV can be predicted as:

$$\begin{aligned} y_{max} &= [u_{j+1}(0) - u_j(T)] K_o (1 + \sigma) \\ &= [u_j(0) - u_j(T) + \gamma e_j(0)] K_o (1 + \sigma) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Thereafter, to define the degree of overshoot, let A denote the maximum value of the desired signal:

$$A = \max_{t \in [0, T]} y_d(t) - \min_{t \in [0, T]} y_d(t) \quad (12)$$

According to (12), the effect of FSV can be controlled by satisfying the following inequality:

$$y_{max} < \alpha A \quad (13)$$

where α is a scale factor that defines the acceptable degree of FSV. From (11), it can be obtained that y_{max} is associated with the learning gain γ at time $t = 0$. Hence, one feasible method is to adjust γ at $t = 0$ to control the degree of FSV. Combining (10), (11), (12) and (13) yields:

$$\gamma \leq \frac{1}{e_j(0)} \left[\frac{\alpha A}{K_o(1+\sigma)} + u_j(T) - u_j(0) \right] = A_c \quad (14)$$

To formulate γ in (14) at $t = 0$, let γ_{st} represent it and be expressed as:

$$\gamma_{st} = A_c \text{sat}(\gamma/A_c) \quad (15)$$

By adjusting the learning gain at $t = 0$ in (15), the effect of FSV on ILC can be reduced. Based on the above analysis and design, the update-law for LGS-ILC in frequency domain is expressed as:

$$U_{j+1}(s) = Q(s)[U_j(s) + \gamma_L E_j(s)] \quad (16)$$

where the time-varying learning gain γ_L is defined as:

$$\gamma_L = \begin{cases} \gamma_{st}, t = 0 \\ \gamma_o, 0 < t \leq T \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

where γ_o is the global learning gain, and $\gamma_{st} = A_c \text{sat}(\gamma_o/A_c)$. The control system diagram of LGS-ILC is displayed in Fig.10, where the learning gain γ_L is switched according to the period, then γ_{st} is updated by the FSV prediction law (15) at the end of each iteration period.

2) *Convergence analysis of LGS-ILC*: Without loss of generality, assuming that a lightly damping resonating system $G(s)$ with open-loop gain K_o is controlled by ILC (2), the learning gain γ_o of which satisfies the convergence condition (3) with a well-designed robust filter $Q(s)$. When modifying (2) to LGS-ILC (16), the following condition should be met to ensure LGS-ILC convergence:

$$0 < \gamma_{st} \leq \gamma_o < 1/K_o \quad (18)$$

The proof is summarized as follows. First, the tracking error of LGS-ILC is written as:

$$E_j(s) = Y_d(s) - Y_j(s) = Y_d(s) - G(s)U_j(s) \quad (19)$$

Assuming γ_L is time-invariant, substituting (19) into (16) yields:

$$\begin{aligned} Y_d(s) - E_{j+1}(s) &= Q(s)[Y_d(s) - E_j(s) + \gamma_L G(s)E_j(s)] \\ \Rightarrow E_{j+1}(s) &= Q(s)[1 - \gamma_L G(s)]E_j(s) + [1 - Q(s)]Y_d(s) \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

By converting (20) into the norm form:

$$\begin{aligned} \|e_{j+1}(t)\|_2 &\leq \|Q(s)[1 - \gamma_L G(s)]\|_\infty \|e_j(t)\|_2 \\ &+ \|1 - Q(s)\|_\infty \|y_d(t)\|_2 \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

For (21), the term $\|Q(s)[1 - \gamma_L G(s)]\|_\infty$ is bounded, thus let $\Psi = \|Q(s)[1 - \gamma_L G(s)]\|_\infty$. Similarly, let $\Theta = \|1 - Q(s)\|_\infty \|y_d(t)\|_2$. Then, (21) is rewritten as:

$$\begin{aligned} \|e_{j+1}(t)\|_2 &\leq \Psi \|e_j(t)\|_2 + \Theta \\ &\leq \Psi^2 \|e_{j-1}(t)\|_2 + (1 + \Psi)\Theta \\ &\leq \dots \leq \Psi^{j+1} \|e_0(t)\|_2 + \Theta \sum_{n=0}^j \Psi^n \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

At $t = 0$, (22) is expressed as:

$$\|e_{j+1}(0)\|_2 \leq \Psi^{j+1} \|e_0(0)\|_2 + \Theta \sum_{n=0}^j \Psi^n \quad (23)$$

According to (23), the tracking error at $t = 0$ is monotonically decayed when $\Psi < 1$ holds, and the error can be converged to zero only if $\Theta = 0$. In low-frequency range that is much lower than the resonant region and is represented as $\omega \in (0, \omega_l]$, it can be obtained:

$$|G(s)| \stackrel{s=j\omega}{=} |G(j\omega)|_{(0, \omega_l]} = K_o \quad (24)$$

Combining (18) into (24) yields:

$$0 < |\gamma_{st} G(j\omega)|_{(0, \omega_l]} \leq |\gamma_o G(j\omega)|_{(0, \omega_l]} < 1 \quad (25)$$

By (25), we get:

$$0 < |C_o(j\omega)|_{(0, \omega_l]} \leq |C_{st}(j\omega)|_{(0, \omega_l]} < 1 \quad (26)$$

where $C_o(j\omega) = 1 - \gamma_o G(j\omega)$ and $C_{st}(j\omega) = 1 - \gamma_{st} G(j\omega)$ are the convergence condition of γ_o and γ_{st} , respectively. In high-frequency range denoted as $\omega \in (\omega_l, \infty)$, since $\sup_{\omega \in (\omega_l, \infty)} |G(j\omega)| = K_r \gg K_o$, where K_r is the amplitude of resonant peak of the plant, the convergence condition can be derived as:

$$|C_{st}(j\omega)|_{(\omega_l, \infty)} \approx \gamma_{st} K_r \leq |C_o(j\omega)|_{(\omega_l, \infty)} \approx \gamma_o K_r \quad (27)$$

Recalling the assumption that γ_o and $Q(j\omega)$ satisfy $|Q(j\omega)C_o(j\omega)| < 1$, the following inequality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} |Q(j\omega)C_{st}(j\omega)|_{(\omega_l, \infty)} &= |Q(j\omega)|_{(\omega_l, \infty)} |C_{st}(j\omega)|_{(\omega_l, \infty)} \\ &\leq |Q(j\omega)|_{(\omega_l, \infty)} |C_o(j\omega)|_{(\omega_l, \infty)} \\ &< 1 \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

By (26) and (28), it is proven that $\Psi < 1$ in (23) holds when condition (18) is satisfied, thus LGS-ILC is converged.

Here, the enhancement of LGS-ILC in reducing FSV, compared to common P-ILC, is further analyzed. Substituting (17) into (7) yields:

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow 0} |Q(s)[1 - \gamma_L G(s)]| = \begin{cases} |1 - \gamma_{st} K_o|, t = 0 \\ |1 - \gamma_o K_o|, 0 < t \leq T \end{cases} \quad (29)$$

From (29), it can be noted that the introduction of γ_{st} may increase the final tracking error at $t = 0$ in low-frequency range ($\gamma_{st} \leq \gamma_o$). From this point of view, the LGS-ILC locally sacrifices the convergence performance at $t = 0$ to handle

the FSV, while common P-ILC suppresses FSV by globally limiting the learning gain. This means that the proposed LGS-ILC significantly reduces the trade-off between convergence performance and FSV mitigation.

3) *Convergence analysis of the control system:* For brevity, the term s is omitted in the following. According to Fig.7, the tracking error of the controller can be obtained as follows:

$$E_{j+1} = Y_d - \frac{G}{1-GP}V = Y_d - M(U_{j+1} + CE_{j+1}) \quad (30)$$

where C and P are the transfer function of PI controller and PPF, respectively. V is the control output, and $M = G/(1-GP)$. Then, from (30) yields:

$$-MU_{j+1} = (1 + MC)E_{j+1} - Y_d \quad (31)$$

Multiplying $-M$ on (16) gets:

$$-MU_{j+1} = -MQ(U_j + \gamma_L E_j) = -MQU_j - MQ\gamma_L E_j \quad (32)$$

Substituting (31) into (32) yields:

$$(1 + MC)E_{j+1} = -Q[1 + M(C - \gamma_L)]E_j + (1 - Q)Y_d \quad (33)$$

Based on (33), the tracking error between two successive iterations can be obtained as follows:

$$E_{j+1} = \frac{-Q[1 + M(C - \gamma_L)]}{1 + MC}E_j + \frac{1 - Q}{1 + MC}Y_d \quad (34)$$

From (34), to ensure tracking error monotonic decays, the following condition must be satisfied:

$$\left| \frac{Q[1 + M(C - \gamma_L)]}{1 + MC} \right| < 1 \quad (35)$$

By (35), the convergence condition of control system is obtained. Thereafter, the final tracking error of the controller is derived. Repeating (34) yields:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{j+1} &= NE_j + \frac{1 - Q}{1 + MC}Y_d \\ &= N \left(NE_{j-1} + \frac{1 - Q}{1 + MC}Y_d \right) + \frac{1 - Q}{1 + MC}Y_d \quad (36) \\ &= \dots = N^{j+1}E_0 + \frac{1 - Q}{1 + MC}Y_d \sum_{k=0}^j N^k \end{aligned}$$

where $N = -Q[1 + M(C - \gamma_L)] / (1 + MC)$. Obviously, when (35) is satisfied, we get $|N| < 1$. Thus, let $\|N\|_\infty = \Xi$, and $\|Y_d\|_2 = \Gamma$. Rewriting (36) in the norm form gives:

$$\|E_{j+1}\|_2 \leq \Xi^{j+1}\|E_0\|_2 + \left\| \left(\frac{1 - N^j}{1 - N} \right) \left(\frac{1 - Q}{1 + MC} \right) \right\|_\infty \Gamma \quad (37)$$

As the number of trials approaches $j \rightarrow \infty$, we have $\lim_{j \rightarrow \infty} \Xi^{j+1} = 0$. Moreover, it is obvious that $\|E_0\|_2 < \infty$. Therefore, it can be obtained from (37):

Fig. 11. Test setup. 1) vibration isolation stage, 2) PC host system, 3) motion stage, 4) vision system, 5) sensor conditioner, 6) PZT voltage amplifier, 7) dSPACE system, 8) capacitive displacement sensor, 9) flexible transfer manipulator, 10) VAU, 11) Needle, 12) Wafer jig, 13) Wafer sample.

$$\|E_{j+1}\|_2 \leq \left\| \frac{1 - Q}{(1 + MC)(1 - N)} \right\|_\infty \Gamma \quad (38)$$

From (38), it can be observed that achieving lower amplitude in the coefficient of the term Γ results in higher tracking accuracy. This means a high amplitude of $1 + MC$ and a low amplitude of N . The former indicates a high gain of the PI controller and PPF, which is restricted by the control constraint. The latter pertains to the LGS-ILC, which was discussed in Section IV.B.1.

V. EXPERIMENTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Test setup

The whole test system is shown in Fig.11(a). The flexible transfer manipulator is fixed on the gantry as shown in Fig.11(b), which is actuated by a pair of PZTs (PSt150/10/60 VS15, COREMORROW) and measured by a pair of capacitive displacement sensors (NS-DCS14, SYMC). A needle is fixed on the end-effector of the manipulator and integrated into the VAU, as shown in Fig.11(c). The control implement is achieved by the dSPACE rapid prototyping simulating system (DS-1007, dSPACE), PZT voltage amplifier (E01.B3, COREMORROW), and VAU voltage amplifier (E-503, PI). The wafer tape and its jig (see Fig.11(d) and Fig.11(e)) are fixed on the motion stage (PRO-3L1A, Aerotech).

B. Experimental study of α tuning for LGS-ILC

To validate the effectiveness of the proposed LGS-ILC, various trajectories with different fundamental frequencies are employed as the desired signal for tracking tests. Three trajectories are included: smooth cosine trajectory, non-smooth triangular trajectory, and CFET trajectory. Each case is tested under both low and high frequency conditions, following the control limitations of nanopositioning system (ranging from 1 % to 10 % of the first frequency of the plant). Only the experimental results for the X-axis are presented, as the results for Z-axis are similar. Each trajectory is tracked 400 iterations.

Fig. 12. Experimental results of α tuning. (a) and (b) $T1$. (c) and (d) $T2$. (e) and (f) $T3$.

TABLE I
EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS OF α TUNING

FSV factor	$T1$		$T2$		$T3$		
	e_{rms}	e_{max}	e_{rms}	e_{max}	e_{rms}	e_{max}	
	(%)		(%)		(%)		
$\alpha = 1$	L	0.75	1.86	0.37	3.31	0.16	2.17
	H	2.40	5.64	3.15	12.65	3.63	12.45
$\alpha = 0.1$	L	0.75	1.79	0.37	3.18	0.13	2.07
	H	2.37	5.67	1.95	10.24	1.64	3.89
$\alpha = 0.05$	L	0.74	1.96	0.44	3.20	0.17	2.77
	H	2.56	5.68	2.01	10.21	1.49	3.29
$\alpha = 0.01$	L	0.73	1.85	0.55	3.32	0.21	3.55
	H	2.86	5.73	2.13	10.78	1.46	3.18

1) $T1$ -Cosine trajectory: By Fig.12(a) and Fig.12(b), it is seen that decreasing α does not significantly improve the LGS-ILC performance at either low or high frequencies. The smoothness of the trajectory curve indicates no impact from acceleration, making the effect of FSV negligible.

2) $T2$ -Triangular trajectory: As shown in Fig.12(c) and Fig.12(d), the improvement of LGS-ILC is not obvious in low-frequency range but is effective in suppressing vibrations in high-frequency range. The sharp corner at the beginning of the trajectory amplifies the influence of FSV in high-frequency cases, where the LGS-ILC proves to be effective.

3) $T3$ -CFET trajectory: From Fig.12(e), the LGS-ILC suppresses initial vibration in low frequency case because the trajectory requires high acceleration to achieve synchronization speed. This effort becomes significant in high frequency case as illustrated in Fig.12(f), where an undershoot with large amplitude is significantly reduced with decreasing α .

4) *Experimental results analysis*: To analyze the experimental results in detail, the root mean square (e_{rms}) and maximum value (e_{max}) of tracking error are recorded in

Fig. 13. Experimental results in time-domain. (a) and (b) $T1$. (c) and (d) $T2$. (e) and (f) $T3$.

Table.I to assess the tracking performance. It is observed that for low frequency cases of $T1$ and $T2$, LGS-ILC does not effectively improve tracking and even degrades the results when α is excessively decreased. However, in high frequency cases and $T3$, the tracking accuracy is significantly improved by LGS-ILC. This analysis indicates that for low-speed cases within the duration $[u_j(T), u_{j+1}(0)]$ of the desired trajectory, the LGS-ILC should be designed to offer slight effort or without compensation, thus a high value of α should be tuned.

C. Comparative experiments of LGS-ILC

Here, to verify the effectiveness and superiority of the proposed LGS-ILC, several control strategies are applied in tracking tests on the flexible transfer manipulator, with desired trajectories $T1$, $T2$, and $T3$.

1) $C1$ -PI: The commonly used PI controller is employed with the control law $C(s) = K_p + K_i/s$.

2) $C2$ -P-ILC: The P-ILC demonstrated in (2) is used, with a second-order zero-phase low-pass filter applied for $Q(s)$.

3) $C3$ -Energy-selected ILC: An advanced energy-selected ILC proposed in [21] is adopted, where the energy scalar is set as 0.5. For a fair comparison, the learning filter is the same as P-ILC, other than the model-based inversion.

4) $C4$ -LGS-ILC: The proposed LGS-ILC is used for trajectory tracking, where the γ_o is set to the same value as $C2$. The FSV scaling factor is set to $\alpha = 0.1$.

5) *Results in time-domain*: The experimental results in the time-domain are plotted in Fig.13, where $C1$ tracks $T1$, $T2$, and $T3$ with significant lag due to the low mechanical bandwidth. For high-speed $T2$ and $T3$, $C4$ achieves much less vibration compared to ILCs $C2$ and $C3$, demonstrating

TABLE II
COMPARATIVE EXPERIMENT RESULTS.

Controller		T1		T2		T3	
		e_{rms} (%)	e_{max} (%)	e_{rms} (%)	e_{max} (%)	e_{rms} (%)	e_{max} (%)
C1	L	4.33	5.89	4.84	6.55	7.72	22.36
	H	19.07	25.20	12.33	16.03	29.18	25.63
C2	L	0.78	1.84	0.35	3.32	0.16	2.21
	H	2.42	5.63	3.04	12.67	3.61	12.32
C3	L	0.73	1.82	0.34	2.28	0.14	2.04
	H	2.38	5.52	2.91	12.23	2.81	10.37
C4	L	0.74	1.81	0.36	3.15	0.11	2.10
	H	2.35	5.69	1.94	10.80	1.63	3.84

Fig. 14. Experimental results in frequency-domain. (a) and (b) T1. (c) and (d) T2. (e) and (f) T3.

the effectiveness of FSV suppression with C4. Detailed results are recorded in Table.II, indicating that C4 provides superior tracking performance for high-speed trajectories compared to the other controllers. For low-speed cases, the tracking results of C4 are similar to C2 and C3.

6) *Results in frequency-domain*: To further analyze the experimental results, the tracking error in Fig.13 is re-plotted in the frequency domain by Fourier transform, as illustrated in Fig.14. It is seen that the error in the resonant region (180 Hz) for C4 is significantly lower than for C2 and C3, demonstrating that the FSV is effectively addressed by C4. This improvement remains effective in low-speed cases, although the tracking error in the low-frequency range for C4 is slightly worse compared to the other controllers. In addition, by effectively addressing the repetitive error and excluding the non-repetitive error, C3 achieves a lower error compared to C2, while also demonstrating reduced error in the low-frequency range compared to C4. However, the improvement in error within the resonant region, mainly caused by FSV is not evident, as the error is outside the learnable band. In a word, the proposed C4 enhances high-frequency range tracking performance while showing only slight degradation in

Fig. 15. T3 tracking results of flexible transfer manipulator by C4. (a) X-Y trajectory. (b) X-axis. (c) Z-axis.

Fig. 16. CFET experimental results of wafer tape. (a), (c), and (e) The results of Case A, Case B, and Case C by C4. (b) Case C by C1. (d) Case C by C2. (f) Case C by C3.

Fig. 17. Error results by C4. (a) Case A. (b) Case B. (c) Case C.

the low-frequency range, in the presence of a limited learnable band and high-speed tracking requirements.

D. Closed-loop CFET experiments

To verify the effectiveness of the developed system with the designed control strategy, a series of tests are conducted. The motion stage operates in constant velocity mode to simulate the CFET scenario, while the flexible transfer manipulator tracks the CFET trajectory simultaneously. Three experimental cases of CFET are tested, each with different transfer periods and velocities of the motion stage.

- 1) *Case A*: Transfer period: 1000 ms, velocity: 0.1 mm/s.
- 2) *Case B*: Transfer period: 100 ms, velocity: 1 mm/s.
- 3) *Case C*: Transfer period: 50 ms, velocity: 2 mm/s.

4) *Experimental results analysis*: Each case simulates the transfer process 50 times, repeated across three wafer tapes. To demonstrate the motion of needle, the T3 tracking results of the flexible transfer manipulator by the proposed C4 are displayed in Fig.15, where the CFET trajectory is well tracked during the transfer process. To evaluate the test results, the diameter and pitch of holes in the wafer tape are used to characterize the performances. With C4, the hole diameter

TABLE III
PERFORMANCES COMPARISONS OF TRANSFER SYSTEMS

Ref.	Transfer period	Transfer error	Strategy
[4]	100 ms	$\pm 30 \mu\text{m}$	Pick & place
[23]	300 ms	$\pm 5 \mu\text{m}$	Pick & place
[24]	240 ms	$\pm 3 \mu\text{m}$	Flip-COB
[25]	10^4 ms	$\pm 2 \mu\text{m}$	Flip-COB
This work	50 ms	$\pm 2.5 \mu\text{m}$	CFET

remains at $\phi 50 \mu\text{m}$ across all cases, matching the needle diameter, as shown in Fig.16(a), Fig.16(c), and Fig.16(e). In terms of the pitch, the error of the results estimated by the normal fitting (3σ) and margin of error (ME) are recorded in Fig.17, indicates that the largest error is kept within $\pm 2.5 \mu\text{m}$. *C1* fails in *Case B* and *Case C*, while the result of *Case A* is similar to *C4*. Because *C1* cannot provide synchronous motion, the wafer tape is broken in *Case B* and *Case C*, as illustrated in Fig.16(b). Although *C2* and *C3* conduct results similar to *C4* under *Case A* and *Case B*, they fail in high-speed *Case C*, as displayed in Fig.16(d) and Fig.16(f). Scratches are observed behind the hole, and the needle does not fully enter the wafer tape (hole diameter lower than needle diameter). This issue is caused by the undershoot in *T3* tracking, indicating that the needle does not enter synchronous motion promptly. All the results uniformly confirm that the developed system and proposed LGS-ILC successfully keep the needle relatively stationary with the wafer tape during transfer, achieving continuous transfer.

E. Evaluation and discussion

To validate the effectiveness of the proposed CFET strategy, several typical transfer systems presented in [4], [23]–[25] are compared with the developed systems. When assessing the performance evaluation in terms of transfer efficiency and transfer precision, typical quantities used to characterize the performance of the transfer system are as follows: transfer period and transfer error. For a clear comparison, the performances are tabulated in Table.III. As illustrated in Table.III, it is obvious that the CFET strategy demonstrates significant improvement by enabling continuous transfer. Compared with the mentioned approaches, the developed transfer system is capable of simultaneously achieving high-efficiency (50 ms) and high-accuracy ($\pm 2.5 \mu\text{m}$) mechanical transfer.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

A flying ejector-pin system is developed for increasing transfer efficiency, which is enhanced by a novel LGS-ILC. The main contributions are concluded as follows.

- 1) A flying ejector-pin system is proposed to address the drawbacks of high-frequency start-stop manipulation in existing transfer methods, through achieving synchronous motion between the needle and the conveying motion stage.

- 2) To cater for the requirement of high-speed trajectory tracking based on nanopositioning systems, a novel LGS-ILC is proposed and its convergence is proven.
- 3) With the developed transfer system, a series of validation experiments are undertaken, which uniformly verifies the effectiveness and superiority of the proposed LGS-ILC under high-speed trajectory tracking. Additionally, utilizing the designed control strategy, the developed system successfully fulfills continuous transfer.

Even so, the developed mechanical system and control strategy will be further optimized towards high-quality MiniLED mass transfer.

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